

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of 4-Amino-3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carbonitriles and their Derivatives

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2-Phenyl-3-aminoindoles on reaction with benzoyl isothiocyanate furnished the respective *N*-(2-phenyl-3-indolyl)-*N'*-benzoylthioureas, which on hydrolysis with alcoholic sodium hydroxide gave 2-phenyl-3-indolylthioureas (1a-c). These thioureas on condensation with bromoamalonitrile afforded 4-amino-3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carbonitriles (2a-c). On acetylation with acetic anhydride and glacial acetic acid at room temperature, as well as on heating, 2a-c yielded only 4-acetylamino-3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carbonitriles (3a-c) but not the diacetyl derivatives (2a-c). Compounds 3a-c on heating with orthophosphoric acid followed by basification with aqueous ammonia afforded 4-acetylamino-3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carboxamides (4a-c), and under similar conditions, 4-amino-3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carboxamides (5a-c) were obtained directly from 2a-c. Compounds 2a-c on condensation with various isothiocyanates and phenylisocyanate yielded 4-alkyl/(*p*-substituted)-phenylthioureido-3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carbonitriles (6a-c) and 4-phenylureido-3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-4-carbonitriles (7a-c), respectively.

Recently some indolyl carbamates synthesised by us¹ have been found to exhibit antifilarial activity against *Onchocerciasis gutturosa*. Literature survey reveals that 4-aminothiazoles are unstable^{2,3} to acid and base and they are weakly basic in nature³. However Gewald⁴ proved that the 4-aminothiazoline-5-carbonitriles and carboxamides are quite stable and this stability is attributed to the presence of carbonyl group, and thus the extended conjugation or hydrogen bonding would inculcate the stability. In view of these conflicting reports, it was planned to synthesise some indolylthiazolines, study their reactions to establish their stability and screen them for antimicrobial activity. The presence of very reactive functional groups like COOR, CONH₂, CN etc., in aminothiazolines at *ortho*-position to the amino group not only increases the stability but also such compounds serve as very good intermediates for the synthesis of new heterocyclic systems. Introduction of a nitrile or carboxamido group at position *ortho* to amino group on thiazoline moiety otherwise makes these compounds easier to handle.

The *o*-aminonitriles are widely used in making a variety of heterocyclic systems, particularly fused pyrimidines⁴. We report here the convenient synthesis of 4-amino-3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carbonitriles and further use them in the synthesis of a new heterocyclic system. It is also of interest to synthesise thiazoline carrying indole moiety as one of the substituents at position-3 of thiazoline molecule which may exhibit some good biological activity.

Results and Discussion

2-Phenyl-3-aminoindoles were prepared from the corresponding 2-phenylindoles by the literature

method⁵. The 3-aminoindoles on refluxing with ammonium thiocyanate and benzoyl chloride in acetone yielded the *N*-(2-phenyl-3-indolyl)-*N'*-benzoylthioureas, which on hydrolysis with alcoholic sodium hydroxide for 0.5 h gave 2-phenyl-3-indolylthioureas⁶ (1a-c). These were used as the starting materials for the synthesis of 4-aminothiazolines.

By the bromination of malononitrile⁷, crude bromoamalonitrile was obtained in aqueous solution which when condensed with ethanolic solutions of substituted-2-phenylindolyl-3-thioureas (1a-c) yielded hydrobromides of 4-amino-3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carbonitriles (2a-c) (Scheme 1). These compounds on basification with aqueous ammonia solution furnished free bases of 2a-c in good yields (85-90%).

The bromoamalonitrile was also separated from the aqueous layer from ether and it was condensed with various indolyl-3-thioureas in alcoholic solution to get compounds 2a-c. Compounds 2a-c underwent acetylation quite readily with acetic anhydride and acetic acid at room temperature to give 4-acetylamino-3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carbonitriles (3a-c) only, but 4-acetylamino-3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carbonitriles could not be obtained even when 2a-c were refluxed with acetic anhydride and acetic acid, the reason may be due to the steric hinderance by phenyl group in the indole moiety at position-2.

The monoacetyl derivatives (3a-c) when warmed with ortho phosphoric acid, the CN group got hydrolysed and after basification with ammonia yielded 4-acetylamino-3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carboxamides (4a-c). Under the same conditions, the 4-amino-3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carboxamides (5a-c) were

obtained from 2a-c. Compounds 5a-c also underwent acetylation on heating with acetic anhydride and acetic acid yielding the same compounds (4a-c) which were also obtained by hydrolysis of 3a-c under above conditions.

inactive against gram-positive organisms. Compounds 4a-c and 5a-c were also moderately active against both types of organisms except 4c which was highly active against *P. aeruginosa*. Among 6a-u and 7a-c, compound 6h was highly active

Scheme 1

All these reactions show that the thiazoline molecule is quite stable towards acid and base.

Further, the condensation of 2a-c with various isothiocyanates afforded 4-alkyl/(p-substituted)-phenylthioureido-3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carbonitriles (6a-u), and 2a-c under similar conditions on condensation with phenyl isocyanate yielded 4-phenylureido-3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carbonitriles (7a-c).

Biological activity: All compounds were evaluated for their antibacterial activity against gram-negative organisms *E. coli*, *P. vulgaris*, *P. aeruginosa*, *K. pneumonia* and gram-positive organisms *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis* by cup-plate method using streptomycin and sulphamethoxazole as standards.

Some of the compounds showed moderate activity at 25 µg concentration. Compounds 2a-c showed moderate activity against both types of the organisms, but 2b showed a higher activity against *P. vulgaris*, and 2a being inactive against *K. pneumonia*. Compounds 3a-c were moderately active against the gram-negative organisms but

against *K. pneumonia*, 6a and 7b against *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis* and 6r against *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis*.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 293 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Varian EM-360L spectrometer and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS D-300 instrument.

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Preparation of bromomalononitrile: To malononitrile (0.1 mol) dissolved in distilled water (100 ml), bromine (2.1 mol) was added slowly with continuous stirring at room temperature during 0.5 h. The resulting aqueous solution of bromomalononitrile was used as such for the synthesis of 2a-c.

4-Amino-3-(5'-methyl-2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carbonitrile (2b): Method (a). 5-Methyl-2-phenylindolyl-3-thiourea (1b; 0.1 mol) dissolved in minimum quantity of ethanol (250 ml)

was added to an ice-cold solution of bromomalononitrile prepared above. The contents were vigorously stirred for 1 h and filtered. The filtrate was basified by aqueous ammonia, kept for 1 h to settle and the resulting solid was washed with water and redissolved in dilute HCl. The solution was filtered to remove the unreacted indolylthiourea if present as an impurity and filtrate was basified with aqueous ammonia. The residue 2b thus obtained was filtered and crystallised from ethanol: ν_{\max} 3 430 (indole NH), 3 325 (=NH), 3 200 (NH₂), 2 220 (C≡N), 1 640 (NH bend) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.55 (1H, s, =NH), 6.55 (2H, br, NH₂), 6.9–7.55 (8H, m, ArH) and 8.35 (1H, s, indole NH); m/z 345 (M⁺), 319, 292, 221 (fragments by the consecutive loss of CN, HCN, CS, HCN respectively from the molecular ion). Compounds 2a–c (83–89%) had m.p.: 2a, 220°; b, 221°; c, 225°.

Method (b). A mixture of bromomalononitrile (0.1 mol) dissolved in acetone (250 ml) and the indolylthiourea (1b; 0.07 mol) was vigorously shaken. Compound 2b was separated as its hydrobromide which was filtered, washed with acetone and dried. The dried hydrobromide was dissolved in water and basified with aqueous ammonia and the solid separated was crystallised from ethanol. Yield (40%) was very low in this case but purer compound was obtained.

4-Acetylamino 3-(5'-methyl-2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carbonitrile (3b): Compound 2b (0.1 mol) was dissolved in a mixture of acetic anhydride and glacial acetic acid (1:1; 5 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h and poured into cold water. The resulting solid was washed with little ethanol and crystallised from ethanol: ν_{\max} 3 430 (indole NH), 1 640 (NH bend) and 1 595 cm⁻¹ (C=N); m/z 387 (M⁺), 344, 318, 291, 247 and 220 (due to the sequential loss of CH₃CO, CN, HCN, CS and HCN fragments respectively from the molecular ion). Compounds 3a–c (86–90%) had m.p.: 3a, 288°; b, 282°; c, 292°.

4-Acetylamino-3-(5'-methyl-2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carboxamide (4b): Compound 3b (0.1 mol) was warmed in orthophosphoric acid (15 ml) for 10 min and after cooling the reaction mixture was poured into cold water and basified with aqueous ammonia. The product separated was crystallised from pyridine: ν_{\max} 3 340 (indole NH), 3 310 (=NH), 3 200 (acetamide NH), 1 665/1 650 (C=O acetyl/amide), 1 640 (NH bend) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N). Compounds 4a–c (76–83%) had m.p. > 300°.

4-Amino-3-(5'-methyl-2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carboxamide (5b): Compound 5b was also prepared by following the similar method

described for compound 4b from compound 2b and crystallised from pyridine: ν_{\max} 3 270 (indole NH), 3 250 (=NH), 3 210 (NH₂), 1 655 (C=O), 1 635 (NH bend) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.4 (1H, s, =NH), 6.45 (2H, br, NH₂) and 6.9–7.55 (8H, m, ArH); m/z 363 (M⁺), 319, 248, 221 (for the fragments CONH₂, HCN and CS, HCN lost from the molecular ion). Compounds 5a–c (75–82%) had m.p.s. > 300°.

4-(p-Chloro)phenylthioureido-3-(5'-methyl-2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carbonitrile (6m): A mixture of 2b (0.1 mol) and *p*-chlorophenyl isothiocyanate (0.1 mol) was refluxed in ethanol for 4 h. The solid separated was washed with little ethanol and crystallised from ethanol-benzene mixture: ν_{\max} 3 425 (indole NH), 3 325 (=NH), 3 260/3 190 (NH/NH thiourea), 2 220 (C≡N), 1 645 (NH bend), 1 600 (C=N) and 1 245 cm⁻¹ (C=S); m/z 448 (M⁺). Compounds 6a–u (56–82%) had m.p.: 6a, 262°; b, 225°; c, 250°; d, 236°; e, 230°; f, 235°; g, 246°; h, 245°; i, 170°; j, 255°; k, 242°; l, 208°; m, 234°; n, 235°; o, 265°; p, 228°; q, 258°; r, 250°; s, 152°; t, 222°; u, 218°.

4-Phenylureido-3-(5'-methyl-2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-2-imino-4-thiazoline-5-carbonitrile (7b): Compound 2b (0.1 mol) on treatment with phenyl isocyanate (0.1 mol) under similar conditions described for 6m afforded the product: ν_{\max} 3 450 (indole NH), 3 310 (=NH), 3 290/3 230 (NH/NH urea), 2 220 (C≡N), 1 664 (C=O), 1 640 (NH bend) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N). Compounds 7a–c (50–60%) had m.p.: 7a, 243°; b, 240°; c, 250°.

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